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ACTIVITIES OF THE TATAR DIASPORA IN THE CONTEXT OF AZERBAIJANI-TATAR RELATIONS

Abstract. The development of international cooperation in the field of culture is extremely important, as it ensures broad and in-depth interaction between states and peoples, makes real the possibility of dialogue, unites the cultures of the peoples of the world. Azerbaijan is a multicultural country, home to many peoples and ethnic minorities. Representatives of the peoples inhabiting this region are full citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan, including the Tatars. Tatars take an active part in the economic, social and cultural life of the republic. In modern realities, with sustainable economic growth, successful cultural relations have become the key to the development of interstate relations. The Tatar diaspora, represented by the Permanent Mission of the Republic of Tatarstan in Azerbaijan, the Yashlek Tatar Youth Center, the Tugan Tel Society of Tatar Culture and the Ak Kalfak organization of Tatar women, successfully represents the interests and culture of the Tatar people and supports the development of Azerbaijani-Tatar relations. Communities arrange exhibitions, concerts, film screenings, organize national holidays, festivals and various competitions. The expansion of contacts in the field of science and education, literature and art contributes to the expansion of ideas about the culture and lifestyle of people from different countries, the growth of friendship and mutual understanding between peoples, the progress of world civilization. The activities of the Tatar diaspora create a fertile ground for the development of Azerbaijani-Tatar relations.

Key words: Tatar diaspora of Azerbaijan, Permanent Mission of the Republic of Tatarstan in Azerbaijan, Azerbaijani-Tatar relations, culture, Sabantuy in Azerbaijan.

Introduction. The rulers of the land of fires, over the centuries, created favorable conditions for the development of the peoples inhabiting Azerbaijan. Social, economic reforms had a positive impact on all residents without exception. The tolerant, friendly people of Azerbaijan have always deeply respected the traditions and customs of other peoples. As the scientist R. Abdullayeva rightly put it, “In Azerbaijan for centuries, representatives of all nationalities and confessions live in symbiosis. That is, multiculturalism is not a momentary, but a traditional phenomenon in the realities of Azerbaijan” [1]. The situation has not changed in modern, independent Azerbaijan either. Independent Azerbaijan successfully continued the multicultural traditions established long ago. According to the definition of the scientist F. Mammadov, multiculturalism is “a humanistic worldview and a policy corresponding to it, recognizing the rights of culture of representatives of different peoples living in one country... this is not assimilation, but an equal association and development of people of different ethnic groups and cultures on the principles of integration into a national culture titular nation” [3]. At the legislative level, the leaders of the country have given freedom of choice to small peoples who have been living in the territory of Azerbaijan for centuries. On September 16, 1992, the President of Azerbaijan issued a decree “On the protection of rights and freedoms, state support for the development of languages and cultures of national minorities, small peoples and ethnic groups living in the Republic of Azerbaijan” [4]. It was adopted in order to fulfill the need to create favorable conditions for their further free development.

The interpretation of the main material. The first traces of the presence of Tatars in the lands of Azerbaijan can be found at the beginning of the 18th century. The sources mention that the first Tatars appeared on the lands of Azerbaijan after the Caspian campaign of Peter I in 1722-1723, when the Russian authorities began to build fortifications and shipbuilding in the Caspian region, in particular, by the Turkic peoples of the Russian Empire. Representatives of the Volga Tatars, Chuvashs, Kazan Tatars, who were settled in the city of Baku and its environs, were especially involved in construction work. In 1728, some of them were returned, and some remained [5].

In Azerbaijan, the Tatar diaspora, Tatar culture are successfully represented by the Permanent Mission of the Republic of Tatarstan in Azerbaijan, the Center for Tatar Culture named after Tukay, the Yash Lake Society, the Tatar Culture Society Tugan Tel. Representatives of the Tatar people, as full-fledged citizens of the Azerbaijani society, have a significant impact on the development of the cultural, political and social life of the country. In particular, the permanent representation of the Republic of Tatarstan in Azerbaijan holds various events with the participation of Tatars from all over the world.

An important role in the development of relations between Azerbaijan and Tatarstan is played by the Institute of Architecture and Art of the Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan. For many years, the staff of the institute actively participated in conferences, debates, published scientific works developing relations between our peoples. The Institute continued its activities during the Coronavirus pandemic that swept the whole world, but online. Thus, an international online conference dedicated to the work of artists of the Turkic countries during the period of independence was held at the Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan at the Institute of Architecture and Art. The following countries took part in the conference: Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Russia (Tatarstan), Uzbekistan. Tatarstan was adequately represented by:

Zaatov Ismet with a report – Krym Giray I and the 263rd anniversary (1758) of European theatrical performances in the Turkic-Islamic world

Olga Ulemnova with an article on the topic - Problems and achievements of printed graphics in Tatarstan in the post-Soviet period

Natalya Gerasimova with a report - Modern arts and crafts of the Tatars of the Irkutsk region

Lyudmila Shklyayeva with a report on the topic Features of the folk decorative art of the Tatars at the present stage. All participants of the conference made interesting presentations on the topic.

Cultural events bring a special tone to the Azerbaijani-Tatar relations. Below, the author will analyze a number of particularly significant events. It should be noted that this is only a short part of the cultural and educational work of the Tatar diaspora. On the occasion of the 136th anniversary of the remarkable Tatar poet Gabdulla Tokay, the representation held a number of events. Within the framework of a number of events, the representative office held a children's drawing competition "Tukayakiyatlarenslerle donyasy" – "The Magical World of Tukay's Fairy Tales". At the exhibition

stand of the Permanent Mission of the Republic of Tatarstan in Azerbaijan, drawings of the competition dedicated to the 136th anniversary of Gabdulla Tukay, made by young artists, were exhibited. The works of the finalists of the competition “The Magical World of Tukay’s Fairy Tales” took their rightful place at the exhibition stand of the Permanent Mission. On the day of the 136th anniversary of the great Tatar poet Gabdulla Tukay, the Permanent Mission hosted the awarding of the winners and prize-winners of the children’s drawing contest “The Magical World of Tukay’s Fairy Tales”. The competition was attended by children from 6 to 14 years old. From the Representative Office of the Republic of Tatarstan in Azerbaijan, the winners and participants of the competition were awarded diplomas and memorable gifts. Also, a photo exhibition dedicated to G. Tukay was opened in the Representation. On April 18, the Permanent Mission of the Republic of Tatarstan in the Republic of Azerbaijan hosted the opening of a photo exhibition dedicated to the 136th anniversary of the birth of the great Tatar poet, public figure and translator Gabdulla Tukay. Of particular interest to the visitors were the archival photographs of G. Tukay himself, his family members, colleagues and friends of the poet.

The employees of the representative office pay special attention to holding holidays. The most beloved and revered holiday of the Tatar people is Sabantuy. Sabantuy is an ancient, wonderful holiday that has come down to us from time immemorial, preserving the ancient and rich culture of the ancestors of the Tatar people. This holiday used to be held in the spring, before the start of sowing. Sabantuy is currently held after sowing, at the end of June.. Saban (Khaban) translated from Tatar (Turkic) means a plow, or spring, and tui is a holiday, literally means a plow holiday. It should be noted that the Tatars treat their traditions with deep respect and honor them. It is for this reason that the ancient holiday of the plow, Sabantuy, has survived to this day. The Tatars of Azerbaijan, despite the fact that they are far from their historical homeland, observe their national traditions, celebrate their national holidays with love. In one of the picturesque corners of Azerbaijan, namely in the village of Gechresh, Guba region, the solemn opening of the Tatar national holiday Sabantuy took place. Russian Ambassador to Azerbaijan Mikhail Bocharnikov spoke at this significant event. The welcoming speech of the President of the Republic of Tatarstan Rustam Minnikhanov was read to the guests by the chairman of the Yashlek Tatar Youth Center Diyaz Akhmedzhanov.

The holiday was enriched with national dances and songs, dishes of Azerbaijani and Tatar national cuisines were presented at the holiday, popular representatives of the Tatar stage performed their famous songs. More than 1000 guests participated in the celebration. The guests took an active part in various tournaments, competitions and games. A holiday held at such a level, an indicator that the culture, traditions and customs of their people, the Tatars are worthy, are represented in Azerbaijan as its full-fledged citizens.

Taking an active part in the cultural life of Azerbaijan, the Tatar diaspora successfully participates in events of various themes. Tatar public organizations of Azerbaijan – the Center for Tatar Youth “Yashlek”, the Society of Tatar Culture “Tugan Tel” and the organization of Tatar women “AkKalfak-Baku”, with the support of the Permanent Mission, took part in a landmark event dedicated to the Khydyr Nabi (Khydyr Ilyas) holiday, held in house of culture in Buzovny (a suburb of Baku). Representatives of various nationalities living in Azerbaijan performed at the festive concert: Azerbaijanis, Iranians, Tatars, Avars, Lezghins and Meskhetian Turks. An exhibition was held in the foyer of the House of Culture, where national cuisine, jewelry, musical instruments, clothing items and handicrafts of the participants of the event were presented. At the end of the event, the participants, including the Permanent Mission, were awarded on behalf of the Buzovna Culture Center with gratitude for participating as an honored guest.

In modern realities, with sustainable economic growth, successful cultural relations have become the key to the development of interstate relations. The Tatar diaspora, represented by the Permanent Mission of the Republic of Tatarstan in Azerbaijan, the Yashlek Tatar Youth Center, the Tugan Tel Society of Tatar Culture and the AkKalfak-Baku organization of Tatar women, successfully represents the interests and culture of the Tatar people and supports the development of Azerbaijani-Tatar relations. Representatives of the Tatar people, as full-fledged citizens of the Azerbaijani society, have a significant impact on the development of the cultural, social, and political life of the country. The successful activity of the Tatar diaspora creates a fertile ground for the further development of the Azerbaijani-Tatar relations.

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TATAR DİASPORUNUN FƏALİYYƏTİ AZƏRBAYCAN-TATAR QARŞILIQLI ƏLAQƏLƏRİNİN KONTEKSTİNDƏ

Mədəniyyət sahəsində beynəlxalq əməkdaşlığın inkişafı son dərəcə vacibdir, çünki o, dövlətlər və xalqlar arasında geniş və dərin qarşılıqlı əlaqəni təmin edir, dialoq imkanlarını reallaşdırır, dünya xalqlarının mədəniyyətlərini birləşdirir. Azərbaycan multikultural ölkədir, çoxlu xalqların və etnik azlıqların vətənidir. Bu diyarda yaşayan xalqların nümayəndələri Azərbaycan Respublikasının tamhüquqlü vətəndaşlarıdır, o cümlədən tatarlar. Tatarlar respublikanın iqtisadi, sosial və mədəni həyatında fəal iştirak edirlər. Müasir reallıqlarda davamlı iqtisadi artımla uğurlu mədəni əlaqələr dövlətlərarası münasibətlərin inkişafının açarına çevrilmişdir. Tatarıstan Respublikasının Azərbaycandakı Daimi Nümayəndəliyi, Yaşlek Tatar Gənclər Mərkəzi, “Tuqaq Tel” Tatar Mədəniyyət Cəmiyyəti və Tatar qadınlarının “Ak Kalfak” təşkilatı tərəfindən təmsil olunan tatar diasporu tatarların maraqlarını və mədəniyyətini uğurla təmsil edir və Azərbaycan-Tatar münasibətlərinin inkişafına dəstək verir. İcmalar sərgilər, konsertlər, film nümayişləri, milli bayramlar, festivallar və müxtəlif müsabiqələr təşkil edirlər. Elm və təhsil, ədəbiyyat və incəsənət sahəsində əlaqələrin genişlənməsi müxtəlif ölkələrdən olan insanların mədəniyyəti və həyat tərzini haqqında təsəvvürlərin genişlənməsinə, xalqlar arasında dostluğun və qarşılıqlı anlaşmanın artmasına, dünya sivilizasiyasının tərəqqisinə xidmət edir. Tatar diasporunun fəaliyyəti Azərbaycan-tatar münasibətlərinin inkişafı üçün münbit zəmin yaradır.

Açar sözlər: Azərbaycanın tatar diasporu, Tatarıstan Respublikasının Azərbaycandakı daimi nümayəndəliyi, Azərbaycan-tatar qarşılıqlı əlaqələri, mədəniyyət, Azərbaycanda Sabantuy.

Эллада Аббасова (Азербайджан)

ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ТАТАРСКОЙ ДИАСПОРЫ В КОНТЕКСТЕ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНО-ТАТАРСКИХ ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЕЙ

Развитие международного сотрудничества в сфере культуры имеет чрезвычайно большое значение, так как оно обеспечивает широкое и углубленное взаимодействие между государствами и народами, делает реальной возможность диалога, соединяет культуры народов мира. Азербайджан мультикультуральная страна, являющаяся родиной для многих народов и этнических меньшинств. Представители народов заселявших этот край, являются полноправными гражданами республики Азербайджан, в том числе и татары. Татары принимают активное участие в экономической, социальной и культурной жизни республики. В современных реалиях при устойчивом экономическом росте, успешные культурные взаимоотношения стали залогом развития межгосударственных отношений. Татарская диаспора в лице Постоянного представительства Республики Татарстан в Азербайджане, Центра татарской молодежи «Яшьлек», Общества татарской культуры «Туган тел» и организация татарских женщин «Ак калфак» успешно представляет интересы и культуру татарского народа и поддерживает развитие азербайджано-татарских взаимосвязей. Общины устраивают выставки, концерты, просмотр кинолент, занимаются организацией национальных праздников, фестивалей и различных конкурсов. Расширение контактов в сфере науки и образования, литературы и искусства способствует расширению представлений о культуре и образе жизни людей разных стран, росту дружбы и взаимопонимания между народами, прогрессу мировой цивилизации. Деятельность татарской диаспоры создает благоприятную почву для развития азербайджано-татарских взаимосвязей.

Ключевые слова: татарская диаспора Азербайджана, Постоянное представительство Республики Татарстан в Азербайджане, азербайджано-татарские взаимосвязи, культура, Сабантуй в Азербайджане.